

TECHNOLOGICAL TRAINING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Djandosova Svetlana Tashbayevna

teacher of State public school number 307 Tashkent

Annotation: One of the main requirements for the introduction of the Federal state educational standard (hereinafter FSES) is the inclusion of younger students in active creative activity. Very effective and interesting are integrated classes that combine applied and visual art. As part of the implementation of the Federal state educational standard of primary General education (hereinafter referred to the GEF DOE), technology lessons have great educational opportunities and they need and it is important to carry out. Children in these lessons learn to choose, combine and come up with their own means of expression, using known techniques and methods. The peculiarity of the technology lesson in primary school within the framework of implementation is the formation of technological worldview and technological culture, education of labor, civil and Patriotic qualities of the younger generation.

Key words: Technology lessons, primary school, project method, Federal state educational standard of primary General education, extracurricular activities.

Introduction. Unpredictability is a real feature of our modern life. Everything around is changing with imperceptible speed. It is in such a rapidly changing modern world that the educational achievements of students cannot be limited only to the development of subject knowledge, skills and abilities. A modern teacher should strive to teach a student to learn in a creative way, aimed at independently acquiring and mastering new knowledge, and not just sitting and taking ready-made truths. A feature of the GEF IEO is their activity character, which sets the main task of developing the student's personality. Modern education refuses the traditional presentation of learning outcomes in the form of knowledge, skills and abilities; GEF formulations indicate real activities. The contents of the programs of educational organizations on technology in elementary school are developed taking into account the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard, and system-activity, health-saving, humane-personal and cultural approaches are used as the conceptual foundations of this academic subject. The main goal of studying the subject of technology is to deepen the general educational preparation of schoolchildren, the formation of their spiritual culture and the comprehensive development of the personality based on the integration of conceptual (abstract), visual-figurative and visual-effective components of cognitive activity. Its study contributes to the development of the creative abilities of the individual, creative abilities, ingenuity,

intuition, as well as creative self-realization and the formation of motivation for success and achievements based on subject-transforming activity. The technology lesson differs in many ways from the lessons in other subjects, especially the humanities. The subject of technology is unique in that schoolchildren learn to use the knowledge gained in other lessons in this subject in everyday practical activities, which naturally contributes to their socialization. The most demanded technologies at the lessons are modern educational technologies. The most optimal, for the implementation of the activity of students in the classroom, are group forms of work. The role of group work in the classroom cannot be underestimated. For the student, there is an opportunity to visit different images - from a leader to a consultant, from a theorist to a practitioner. This form of work at the technology lesson will allow the class team to become more cohesive and at the same time develop the individuality of each. It's no secret that some children are afraid to go to the blackboard to answer in front of the class and the teacher. In the group, such a child will receive approval and support and, accordingly, earn the praise of the teacher. The situation of success will contribute to the development of confidence and independence of the student. At this stage, it is used: work in groups, work in pairs, and subsequently - work in a team method. Such non-standard technology lessons in elementary school expand the possibilities of the subject, bring in an atmosphere of competitive spirit, creativity, and self-expression of younger students. The method of projects in technology lessons is not new and has been used for a long time. It is understood as a way of organizing the cognitive and labor activity of students in order to solve problems associated with the design, creation and manufacture of a real object - a product of labor. When determining the topics of educational projects in the primary grades, one should be guided by the content of the training. At the same time, the teacher must take into account the feasibility of the object of labor for younger students of the appropriate age, as well as its social or personal value. The projects carried out at the technology lessons are practice-oriented, as they are aimed at solving a social problem of an applied nature. These projects involve a practical outcome - a product that satisfies a specific need. In the process of working on a project, diligence, the ability to make decisions independently, responsibility, communication skills, and ingenuity are brought up; positive needs and interests are formed, which contributes to self-determination and self-realization of students.

One of the important ways to conduct meaningful, creative and interesting work with primary school students in a technology lesson is the use of information technology. A new generation of students is interested in getting involved in the field of multimedia technologies. Research work, creative activity, motivation, independence, search for material, discovery of a new one develop more effectively. The most important task of the modern education system is the formation of a set of

universal educational activities that provide the competence to "teach to learn", and not just the development of specific subject knowledge and skills by students. The main educational value of classes using information technology lies in the fact that they allow you to create a multi-sensory interactive environment of education with almost unlimited potential opportunities that are at the disposal of both the teacher and the student. Unlike conventional technical means of education, information technologies allow not only to saturate the student with a large number of concepts, but also to develop the intellectual, creative abilities of children, their ability to independently acquire new knowledge, work with various sources of information. A modern lesson, built in accordance with the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard, contributes to the formation of educational motivation, creative and cognitive activity, independence, responsibility; critical and artistic-figurative thinking of younger schoolchildren. Technology, as an academic subject, has great potential for creating conditions for the cultural and personal development of schoolchildren. The social order of society in the field of teaching technology puts forward the task of developing the personality of students, strengthening the humanistic content of education, more fully realizing the upbringing, educational and developmental potential of the subject in relation to the individuality of each student.

List of used literature:

1. Valeeva G.Kh., Kuvaeva. M.M., Musin Sh.R., Chigrov M.N. Preparing future teachers for the organization of extracurricular activities. Educational and methodological manual - Sibay: Sibay city printing house - branch of the State Unitary Enterprise of the Republic of Belarus Publishing House "Republic of Bashkortostan", 2017. - 80 p.
2. Valeeva G.Kh., Kuvaeva M.M., Musin Sh.R. Professional and pedagogical training of future teachers of technology Teaching aid - Sibay: Sibay Information Center - branch of the State Unitary Enterprise of the Republic of Belarus Publishing House "Republic of Bashkortostan", 2018. - 118 p.
3. Zolotareva A.V. Problems and prospects for the inclusion of additional education for children in the process of implementing the Federal State Educational Standard of General Education // Vneshkolnik, 2011. - No. 3 - P. 15-18.
4. Leontovich A.V., “Research activity of students” (collection of articles), M. 2014

